

Vietnam

Introduction

Under the United Nations' Agenda 2030, one indicator of progress towards the conservation of mountain ecosystems (SDG 15.4) is the percentage [%] coverage of important sites for mountain biodiversity (**key biodiversity areas, KBAs**) by **protected areas (PAs)** (SDG 15.4.1). KBAs are areas that significantly contribute to the persistence of global biodiversity. Currently, the indicator is hosted by the UN Environment Programme World Conservation Monitoring Centre (WCMC).

WCMC site-based: The indicator is officially calculated as the **average of the PA coverage of KBAs within a country that are considered mountainous** based on the WCMC mountain definition from 2000¹.

GMBA area-based: As an alternative, the Global Mountain Biodiversity Assessment (GMBA) calculates the indicator as the **ratio between the total area of protected KBAs and the total area of KBAs in mountains**, applying its latest mountain definition from 2022².

Unless mentioned otherwise, the data presented in this one-pager correspond to the GMBA area-based calculation approach, for countries that have KBA in mountains (n = 190).

WCMC site-based versus GMBA area-based (temporal comparison)

Vietnam in an international context (2020)

In the left side figure, each point represents one country and its indicator value with both the WCMC site-based and the GMBA area-based calculation approach. Vietnam is marked with the asterisk. Countries close to the diagonal line have a similar indicator value for both calculation approaches, not taking into account the mountain area of a country.

Vietnam, with a GMBA area-based **indicator value of 48.5 for 2020**, has a value lower than 95 other countries. 94 countries have a value lower than Vietnam.

Looking at the spatial disaggregation of mountains in Vietnam (overleaf), eight mountain ranges are transboundary and need a cross-border management.

¹ Kapos et al. (2000) doi:10.1079/9780851994468.0004

² Snelhage et al. (2022) doi:10.1038/s41597-022-01256-y

Percentage of KBA cover versus percentage of KBA covered by PA

Subnational indicator values

From the ten mountain ranges in Vietnam, two are without KBA (pinkish coloring in the country map). From the other eight (left side figure), one has an indicator value of at least 95% but is not fully protected.

Explore GMBA's global coverage of important sites for mountain biodiversity by protected areas, visit:
gmba.unibe.ch/services/indicators/sdg_1541